

APPLICATION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES TO THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.

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Abstract: The article talks about the importance of introducing information technologies to the process of teaching physical education and sports.

Methods: Changing teaching methods by expanding the importance of pedagogical technologies that form practical skills of information analysis, independent work, increasing the role of independent work of students. Implementation of pedagogical technologies is a consciously organized, socially determined, targeted activity system aimed at improving practice based on scientific and pedagogical recommendations. Implementation is to accept, understand, implement, and feel the effectiveness of an idea or recommendation in the results of one's activities. This allows the introduction of multimedia educational materials, new information and telecommunication technologies into the educational process.

Results: Enormous possibilities for activating the knowledge activity of students through the use of information technologies in the educational process, and for their effective implementation, require didactic understanding and a clear connection with the general laws of this activity and the laws of activation. Also, mandatory consideration of individual intellectual and physical capabilities of students. This, in turn, should encourage scientific research in the field of physical education and sports education, information technology, and their wide application in the practice of the professional training of specialists in the 21st century model.

Conclusion: The use of various educational tools of information and communication technologies in the educational process allows to solve the following tasks:

- development of the subject field in different levels and in more detail;
- development of skills and abilities to solve typical practical problems in the field of chosen subject;
- development of analysis and decision-making skills in non-standard problem situations;
- development of abilities in certain types of activity;
- conducting educational and scientific experiments with models of studied objects and processes;
- restoration of knowledge, skills and qualifications;
- control and assessment of the level of knowledge and skills.

Keywords: technology, student, teacher, specialist, education, information technology, competence.

Introduction

Due to the creation of organizational, material and technical conditions, modern informational and methodical provision of the educational process with the help of highly qualified pedagogical personnel, the development of personal qualities and abilities of

students, the formation of general cultural and professional competencies that enable the formation of a competitive specialist, all kinds of I will be able to develop creative potential in educational institutions.

Today, the Internet has become an integral part of modern society. Information technologies are constantly updated and actively introduced into the field of education: electronic educational resources are being developed, including in the field of additional education, new interactive forms of education are emerging. Thus, education will be more convenient. In this case, the student needs information culture, without which it is impossible to get knowledge.

- Information culture is a person's ability to correctly use all information technologies in his work.

Information culture assumes that a person uses information technology to solve the tasks set to achieve the goals of his activity: he can plan the sequence of actions necessary to achieve the goal, he can search for the information necessary to solve the problem he knows how to organize, he knows how to work with selected information, organize, systematize, summarize and present it to others in an understandable form, he can communicate with other people using modern IT tools. The modern stage of education is characterized by the use of powerful personal computers, high-speed high-capacity disks, new information and telecommunication technologies, multimedia technologies and virtual reality, as well as a philosophical understanding of the ongoing informatization process and its social consequences. In modern conditions, the informatization of society ensures the mandatory use of computers in education aimed at ensuring computer literacy and information culture of students.

In the teaching of sciences, it will be possible to apply pedagogical methods that allow processing large data in a minimum of time in several areas at the same time, because human memory and thinking receive great support at the stage of selection and comparison of initial data. . At the same time, the position of both the student and the teacher changes significantly, their cognitive and educational activities are constructed in a different way.

The pedagogical aspect is related to the need to determine the most favorable conditions for the implementation of the most important goals of using modern information and communication technologies as a means of education and self-education.

The use of various educational tools of information and communication technologies in the educational process allows to solve the following tasks: - development of the subject field in different levels and in more detail;

- development of skills and abilities to solve typical practical problems in the field of chosen subject;
- development of analysis and decision-making skills in non-standard problem situations;
- development of abilities in certain types of activity;
- conducting educational and scientific experiments with models of studied objects and processes;
- restoration of knowledge, skills and qualifications;
- control and assessment of the level of knowledge and skills.

Changing teaching methods by expanding the importance of pedagogical technologies that form practical skills of information analysis, independent work, increasing the role of independent work of students. Implementation of pedagogical technologies is a consciously

organized, socially determined, targeted activity system aimed at improving practice based on scientific and pedagogical recommendations. Implementation - to accept, understand, implement, and feel the effectiveness of an idea or recommendation in the results of one's activity. This allows the introduction of multimedia educational materials, new information and telecommunication technologies into the educational process. It allows the presentation of educational materials not only in print, but also in graphic, audio, and animated form, which allows many students to learn the material at a high level, to monitor student knowledge, to automate the assessment and correction system, from interactive electronic manuals. use, increase interest in science, formation of information culture.

Enormous possibilities for activating the knowledge activity of students through the use of information technologies in the educational process, and for their effective implementation, require didactic understanding and a clear connection with the general laws of this activity and the laws of activation. Also, mandatory consideration of individual intellectual and physical capabilities of students. This, in turn, should encourage scientific research in the field of physical education and sports education, information technology, and their wide application in the practice of the professional training of specialists in the 21st century model.

At the same time, both the student and the teacher should deeply understand the dual role of information and pedagogical technologies. On the one hand, they serve as a really powerful tool for activating the educational process and activating the educational and cognitive activities of students. On the other hand, information technology itself is one of the most important means of successfully performing many professional functions of a future specialist and a means of forming his information culture as an important element of professional competence.

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